

MASS-MEDIA APPLICATIONS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

The benefits of teaching foreign languages using a variety of media are covered in this article, along with how information and communication technology might be included into the conventional educational process. The work also includes links to websites of foreign public information TV networks and news agencies, as well as a selection of current English-language periodicals and their electronic counterparts. The emergence of digital platforms has transformed the character of contemporary media, rendering it no longer singular. The author highlights the extraordinary efficacy of using real content and a broad range of subjects covered in magazines, the linguistic relevance of mass media resources, and their informational saturation for the development of interlingual and intercultural communication skills and abilities.

Keywords: *intercultural, competence, boosting, deepen, broaden, audience, broadcast, challenge, environment.*

Modern approaches to teaching foreign languages are aimed at the formation of a multicultural personality through the development of foreign language competence, the ability of representatives of different linguistic cultures and communities to effectively interact with each other. It is impossible to overestimate the enormous information and communication potential of modern media. Work with foreign media services is aimed at developing linguo-sociocultural competence and intercultural communication skills within the international community. The main task of the mass media is to convey various types of information - verbal, audio, visual, using the principle of a broadcast channel. The media include such traditional means of transmitting information as the press, radio and television, and relatively new forms of communication with a mass audience in the form of Internet resources, successfully replacing all of the above with online versions of well-known newspapers and magazines, and news agency websites. With all the variety of forms and methods of presenting information to the general public, the newspaper is a key component in the overall mass media complex. This is due, first of all, to the fact that

the newspaper is the oldest mass media in which the formation of the fundamental categories of journalistic style characteristic of the language of the periodical press took place. In addition, this is due to the widest daily availability of the newspaper. Thus, the text array of the newspaper is still noticeably superior to all other media. It is worth noting that “the educational capabilities of mass media texts are enormous: firstly, it is a rich linguo thesaurus, reflecting all the nuances of the movement of the language norm; secondly, it is an inexhaustible living source of sociocultural information about the country of the language being studied; and finally, the material of media texts allows you to solve a wide range of methodological tasks: from consolidating vocabulary to improving oral speech skills. Representing an excellent example of modern speech use, mass media texts are included in most English language textbooks of various levels and directions” [Dobrosklonskaya,2005].

Today it is a great undertaking and a challenge to prepare the future-to-be teachers, to use effectively the new technology. Training in-service teachers is lacking a lot. Education technology training for teachers should be a part of in-service teacher training and a crucial part for pre-service teacher training as well. This may be done through seminars for in-service teachers and through putting it in the curricula of the teacher preparing universities for the future to be teachers. We need to find ways to help teachers be competent, confident and creative users of technology. Through exercises utilizing newspapers, magazines, radio, TV, movies, books, the Internet, and other media, students can practice their language skills in reading, writing, speaking, and listening. They also provide a ton of activities for the pupils to do both inside and outside the classroom. encouraging extensive reading by boosting enthusiasm and providing the pupils with the self-assurance and tools to carry on reading outside of the classroom. The media deepens and broadens our comprehension while keeping us up to date on global events. Information is readily available these days and comes from a variety of sources, however we should attempt to take advantage of this information, discover topics that interest us, recognize concerns that affect us, learn about particular issues, and become aware of issues, opportunities, and resources. It is therefore simple to obtain this information, but harder to decide which to use and even harder to implement in the classroom.

The modern world of universal digitalization has embraced all spheres of our lives, thereby launching a rather painful process of falling print circulation. The closest rival and competitor of the printed newspapers and magazines we are used to is the multimedia space with its truly limitless resources. If twenty years ago we literally “hunted” for authentic material from abroad on paper, today almost all periodicals from around the world are available in the original on the day the issue

goes to press. Moreover, the feedback mechanism began to actively develop, as the audience was given the opportunity to express their opinions, and the nature of the mass media ceased to be unidirectional. Thanks to the communication and educational capabilities of the Internet, anyone can get the latest information from social networks or use the electronic version of world-famous and influential print and broadcast media. Taking into account the effectiveness of using authentic material and the wide range of topics covered in periodicals, as well as taking into account the specifics of the modern readership that has moved to the Internet, the emergence of specialized magazines for online. Thanks to the variety and novelty of the proposed material, as well as the information and methodological support of the above-mentioned publications, students learn and enrich their vocabulary more successfully and with great pleasure, improve their listening comprehension of foreign language speech, and broaden their horizons. The formation of audiovisual competencies in teaching foreign languages is facilitated by video resources of international public information television channels and news agencies: BBCNews, SkyNews, Euronews, FoxNews, CNN, Reuters. These can be either video recordings of news or online reports. It is noteworthy that almost any video can be accompanied by a transcript or subtitles, built-in online dictionaries, which remove language difficulties when mastering new lexical units. Many media companies specifically develop a set of exercises and tasks designed for a certain level of language proficiency. Video news offers a wide variety of language and speech samples, as they can include different regional accents, specialized and professional vocabulary and features of grammatical structures, and cultural features. While watching an authentic video, phonetic norms are memorized on a subconscious level, attention is focused on the differences in the pronunciation norms of the English and American varieties of the language, regional accents and dialects [Ivanova,2016].

The main feature of the news format on television is a certain ratio of text content, video and sound . The Internet maintains students' interest in new, constantly changing and expanding sources of information that the teacher can use in the learning process. The Internet can be considered simultaneously as a learning environment (interactive tasks on educational sites, viewing news in real time, distance learning) and as a source of educational materials of varying quality, type and form [Raitskaya,2004]. There is no doubt that the integration of communicative tasks created on the basis of the living language of mass media into traditional forms of teaching foreign language communication can effectively form and improve not only linguistic and speech competence students, but also the ability to use information and communication technologies in the process of independent and autonomous

learning, thereby making it possible to bring the entire process of education and self-education to a qualitatively new level.

Institutions of higher education ought to encourage the adoption of new technologies, viewing them as instructional aids that will help teachers and students become technologically literate. To facilitate learning for both educators and students, schools ought to allocate more funds towards purchasing hardware. With software, they should be aware of the links between schools, inside schools, and on a professional development level, providing tools to support teachers in integrating technology into the curriculum and classroom. Universities must make considerable choices about how much to invest on technology, how best to achieve their educational goals and how fast they wish to deploy recent technology. This is an imperative task, because ‘technology facilitates deep exploration and integration of information, high level thinking and profound engagement, by allowing students to design, explore, experiment, access information and model complex phenomena. This is what we all want for our schools, our teachers and our students, the best’. [Lawrence Tomei, 2002]

Teachers can easily create a visual learning environment (friendly for visual learners) with the use of multimedia. In addition to being a picture that speaks a thousand words, a picture fosters imagination, critical thinking, and observation in pupils. Whether the subtitles are on or not, seeing the film improves visual learners. Playing music on the radio facilitates improved learning for auditory learners. It is obvious that having the script after listening to the recording will benefit both visual and auditory learners. We may improve and, when needed, advance students' comprehension in the classroom by utilizing a variety of media. When it comes to providing feedback and training, Reflective Teaching, evaluating and synthesizing, measuring students' progress over time, modifying certain options, testing, peer coaching, and other related activities, using audio and video with student teachers is essential. In addition to helping students improve accuracy and fluency, media can assist with a wide range of issues, including: motivation, clarity, recycling, drafting, revising, editing, variety, mixed-ability classes, updating information in textbooks, and bringing life and color to classroom procedures and methods. There are many problems that the media either cannot or should not tackle. Three key uses of the internet exist for education. It can be used as a location to learn and publish, as well as a place to collaborate and obtain information. It was believed a few years ago that computers will eventually replace instructors, but this did not pan out. An alternate method of teaching and learning that emphasizes using computers to help students solve real-world problems while they are studying is computer-based instruction. But no matter how advanced it gets, teachers will always be needed.

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